

MONITORING OF TOTAL MERCURY IN AIR OF THE FORMER MERCURY MINE AND IN THE VICINITY OF THE CEMENT PRODUCTION FACILITY

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Abstract

This project quantified atmospheric gaseous elemental mercury (GEM) and total gaseous mercury (THg) concentrations in Idrija, the former mercury (Hg) mine and the cement production facility, Salonit-Anhovo, located in Slovenia using three air Hg monitoring techniques, namely; the Tekran system, Lumex RA-915M, and biomonitoring using lichens. Hg emission data were recorded from the cement facility.

Continuous GEM atmospheric concentration measurements were performed using the Tekran system over one year (December 6, 2019 – December 31, 2020) at Vodarna in the cement plant vicinity. GEM concentration values recorded from the Tekran system range from 0.1 ng/m³ – 29.5 ng/m³. Wind direction plays an important role in atmospheric Hg concentrations. The analysis revealed that strong winds in the direction of the Vodarna from the cement plant and high levels of Hg emissions from the plant emanating influenced high GEM concentrations in this particular sampling location.

GEM concentrations were also measured using the Lumex detector at all sampling locations. GEM concentrations in the vicinity of the former Idrija smelting plant recorded higher values (up to 78.2 ng/m³) compared to values recorded at the cement plant vicinity and the reference location on Pokljuka (up to 2 ng/m³). Also, a comparison of the past and present measurement trends of Hg in air showed a decrease from 20 000 – 14 ng/m³ at the smeltery site and 6 000 – 4 ng/m³ within the Idrija town between 1974 – 2020.

THg in in situ (*Punctelia subrudecta* and *Flavoparmelia caperata*) and transplanted lichen samples (*Hypogymnia Physodes*) were conducted for a period of 3 and 6 months respectively. Lichens were analysed after proper preparation by AAS detector Model Hg-

201 Semi-automated Hg Analyzer. Results from both the in situ and transplanted lichens showed that lichens are very sensitive to air contamination and are known to accumulate compounds and elements in amounts that closely correlate with atmospheric levels. Also, after comparing the results of THg in lichens and GEM measurements using the air active measurements, a strong positive correlation was obtained, indicating that lichens can be used as a cost-effective technique for Hg monitoring.

1. Introduction

Hg is considered a global pollutant and can be transported to long distances in the atmosphere, transformed between different species and has the potential to accumulate in the food chain. Hg in the atmosphere exist as GEM, Hg^{2+} (gaseous oxidized mercury) and particulate bound mercury (PBM) (Horowitz et al., 2017b; Streets et al., 2017; UNEP 2018). Elemental mercury (Hg°) in a smaller proportion from the troposphere is vertically released into the stratosphere and deposited back into the troposphere after oxidizing to Hg^{2+} . Hg is toxic in almost all chemical forms including organic Hg complexes consisting of mono-methylmercury (CH_3Hg^+ or MeHg) and monoethylmercury ($\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{Hg}^+$) species and dimethylmercury (DMeHg), inorganic Hg (Hg^{2+}) and elemental Hg (Hg°). Hg toxicity depends on the chemical form, route and mode of exposure (inhalation vs injection; acute vs chronic), dosage and victim susceptibility. The degree of Hg toxicity has received prompt attention from the scientific community, governments and stakeholders across the globe. The Minamata tragedy resulting from Hg poisoning and many other scenarios stimulated the adoption and development of innovative and technological ways of addressing this concern. Several commercial devices have been developed to measure Hg species presence in a more precise, accurate and efficient way, and recovery and treatment technologies to retrieve Hg in contaminated waste. These new technologies are developed to reduce emissions from anthropogenic activities, remove Hg efficiently from the soil and solid waste, water bodies, and also quantify Hg speciation for risk assessment (Pavlish et al., 2003; Horvat et al., 2003; Chen et al., 2012; Essa et al., 2015; Han et al., 2019). Hg in the environment is transported by environmental mechanisms such as wind flux, runoff and dry and wet deposition. Hg has no transportational boundaries and as a result exists in all environmental media, making living organisms exposure to Hg difficult to avoid.

Frequent measurements of Hg species in the atmospheric environment are of high significance in the understanding of the behaviour of Hg. Identification of different forms of mercury is important for mercury analysis. Mercury is detected by atomic absorption (AAS) or atomic fluorescence spectrophotometry (AFS) (Tekran 1998; Gustin et al., 2015). Both detectors are frequently used to accurately measure Hg due to their simplicity. However, the original forms of mercury in the sample are destroyed in the process (Lu et al., 1998).

Atmospheric Hg measurement remains a big challenge. Despite all the interferences affecting atmospheric mercury measurements, studies have grouped atmospheric Hg measurements interferences in contaminated sites into; meteorological factors (e.g. atmospheric pressure, air temperature, wind speed and turbulence, solar radiation, snow cover) (Gustin et al., 2002; Gronlund et al., 2005; Kotnik et al., 2005; Kocman et al., 2011; Kocman and Horvat, 2011; Llanos et al., 2011; Ljubic-Mlakar et al., 2011); soil moisture content (Gustin and Stamenkovic, 2005; Kotnik et al., 2005; Kocman et al., 2011; Kocman and Horvat, 2011); soil temperature and surface characteristics (Beckers and Rinklebe, 2017); and, air mixing (Bahlmann and Ebinghaus, 2003). These factors control the temporal variability of mercury emissions. Horvat et al., (2000), Kotnik et al., (2005), Kocman et al., (2011) and Kocman and Horvat, (2011)

The purpose of this project is to monitor and quantify gaseous elemental Hg (GEM) in the atmosphere in different heavily polluted sites, such as the former Hg mine in Idrija influence area and surroundings of the cement plant in Anhovo. Hg in the atmosphere was determined using different measurement systems and the results were compared. The study also focuses on the current limitations of these approaches.

2. Methodology

2.1 Sampling/Study Sites

The study was performed in one of the world's most Hg polluted areas, in the vicinity of the former Hg mine in Idrija, and near cement plant Anhovo, that could be the main source of atmospheric Hg in the region. A total of fourteen sampling stations were identified covering the vicinity of the former Hg mine, near the cement plant Anhovo and Pokljuka as presented in Table 3.1.

2.1.1 Idrija

The Idrija mine was the world's second-largest Hg mine located 60 km W from Ljubljana. The Municipality of Idrija reaches an area of 294 km² and numbers around 12,000 inhabitants. The area is populated with about 40 inhabitants per km². Located at the meeting point of the Prealpine world and the Karst, the town of Idrija lies above the second-largest Hg ore deposit on our planet. Previous Hg mining activities from Idrija such as ore processing and disposal of residues in river banks or rivers contributed to Hg deposition within the area (Kocman et al., 2011). The Idrijca River is the major natural transport system for Hg from the former Hg mining area of Idrija to the Gulf of Trieste in N Adriatic Sea (Hines et al. 2000; Kocman et al., 2011). The Idrijca River flows through the town of Idrija and merges with the Soča River (Isonzo in Italy) about 40 km downstream from Idrija. Yearly precipitation ranges between 2400 and 5200 mm/yr. 80 % of the entire topography is covered with forests, whereas agricultural surfaces cover fewer than 20 %, and urban areas represent less than 1 %.

Over 500 years of Hg mining activities in Idrija resulted in Hg contamination within the region. During mining activities, mining waste or residues were deposited to the land, rivers, or on the banks of rivers. This has resulted in a large widespread Hg contamination in soil, water, sediment, and air. Hg⁰ and cinnabar (HgS) were the two forms of Hg extracted during the active years of mining. The major sources of Hg released into the atmosphere are evaporation of Hg⁰ from the heavily polluted surroundings of the former smelting plant and contaminated neighbouring surroundings, and dispersion of Hg bound to particles into the atmosphere due to human activities. Mercury was discovered in Idrija in the late 15th century. Mining and smelting operations lasted until 1995. Idrija is one of the few places in the world where Hg occurs in both its elemental liquid state and as cinnabar ore, producing more than 13% of the world's output. In 500 years of mining history 3 million tons of ore were excavated, from ore about 153 309 tonnes of Hg were

extracted with 107 692 tonnes of commercial Hg. More than 40 000 tonnes of Hg were lost into the local environment. That ranks the Idrija area among the most Hg-polluted areas in the world.

In the Idrija influence area, three locations were selected for the sampling of transplanted and in-situ lichens and active air measurements:

- Idrija-Topilnica: it is an area where the smelting plant operated during the active years of Hg mining. The former smelting plant was transformed into a mining museum. The old rotary furnace remains and is still heavily contaminated by Hg. The whole former smelting area remains contaminated with high Hg concentrations in soil, surrounding plants, and the atmosphere. Today, parts of smelting areas are occupied by the Kolektor factory.
- Idrija-Uprava: This is the administrative unit of the former Idrija mine located in the center of the former Idrija town. At the location there are mine ventilation and elevator shafts that are still in operation due to mine maintenance. This site is influenced by past and current mining activities.
- Spodnja Idrija is a settlement on the banks of the Idrijca River in the Municipality of Idrija, about 4 km north of the Hg smelting plant in Idrija. It is less influenced by mining activities than all other Idrija locations.

Figure 3.1: Idrija is located in a deep basin and surrounded by hills (Source: Google Earth 2020).

Figure 3.2: Geographical locations of sampling locations in Idrija where in situ lichens were collected, transplanted lichens were exposed and continuous active air measurements were performed.

2.1.2 The cement plant, Saloni-Anhovo

The cement plant is located at Anhovo in western Slovenia in the narrow valley of the Soča River. The climate in the area is Sub-Mediterranean, showing the influence of the Adriatic Sea. The area has high relief features, mountains, with elevations of up to 787 m above mean sea level. Annual rainfall is 1456 mm in a year from the meteorological measurements station (Bilje, about 30 km S from Anhovo). The topography of the valley, such as high peaks and steep mountains, prevent the free movement of air within the valley.

The cement plant remains the main atmospheric pollution source in the lower Soča valley. During the last decade, there were many investments in the use of alternative fuels to increase energetic efficiency. The factory is the largest such facility in Slovenia,

incinerating more than 100 000 tonnes of waste per year including toxic materials (up to 40 %). Mlakar et al., (2010) calculated Hg mass balances in the plant cycles. The annual emission of mercury represented 40 – 70 % of the Hg inputs by fuels or raw material, while cement clinker contained about 10 % of Hg load. 85 % of the emitted Hg was as Hg^{2+} (g), and about 15 % as Hg^0 (g). Only a small part was emitted as particulate Hg (p).

Figure 3.3: Cement plant anhovo (Source: Salonit Anhovo).

Around the Cement Plant Anhovo four locations (Figure 3.4) were chosen for active air Hg measurements, in-situ and transplanted lichens as passive samplers:

1. Vodarna: on-line air Hg speciation measurements, online TGM measurements, periodic air GEM measurements, in-situ and transplanted lichens;
2. Anhovo: periodic air GEM measurements, in-situ and transplanted lichens;
3. Morsko: periodic air GEM measurements, in-situ and transplanted lichens;
4. Ročinj: periodic air GEM measurements, in-situ and transplanted lichens.

➤ Vodarna is the location that is most affected by the cement plant. It lies in the small village Močila about 1000 m SW from the plant chimney at the almost same

height. More than 60 % of all winds at the location are blowing in SW direction and bring plant flue gasses to the location. This location is cement plant property and is used for pumping water from the Soča River and distributed to the plant.

- Anhovo is a location within the industrial complex about 1600 m SW from the cement plant chimney. It is in the vicinity of the industrial train station at the same altitude as chimney ground.
- Morsko is a small village above the Anhovo cement plant. The location is a residential area nearby the plant approximately 360 m NE from the plant chimney exhaust at the same height as the village.
- Ročinj is 6 km NE from the cement plant up the Soča valley. Its location is near the village of Ročinj, in a narrow valley, a few meters above the Soča River. Among all sampling locations around the Anhovo cement plant, Ročinj should be the least affected by the plant.

Figure 3.4: Geographical locations of sampling and measurement locations in the vicinity of the cement facility.

2.1.3 Pokljuka

Pokljuka is considered as a remote, clean, industrially free area that was used to collect “zero” lichens, and as a reference location to transplanted ones in previous studies (Jeran et al., 1996; 2002; 2007). Pokljuka is a high karst plateau covered with spacious woods in the Julian Alps, one of the most remote areas in Slovenia. It is the largest complete wood covered surface in the Triglav National Park, more than 20 km wide and almost as long. More than 93% of the trees represent spruce. Climate is mostly alpine with an abundance of precipitations, long snow cover, short vegetation period, and temperature extremes (Figure 3.5).

Figure 3.5: Sampling site Pokljuka 2. Collected in-situ lichens from this location were used for transplantation to other sampling sites.

Figure 3.6: Geographical locations of in situ lichens sampling locations at the Pokljuka. Lichens at sampling location Pokljuka 2 were used as reference.

Table 3.1: List of sampling locations where insitu lichens, transplanted lichens, active air measurement were recorded and their geographic coordinates in the former Hg mine, cement production facility and the reference (Pokljuka).

Location	Sampling code	Latitude(°N)	Longitude (°E)
Vodarna	Vodarna	46,06243	13,61903
Anhovo	Anhovo	56,05718	13,61727
Morsko	Morsko	46,07164	13,6323
Rocinj	Rocinj	46,10869	13,68137
Spodnja Idrija	Spodnja Idrija	46,0733	14,02455
Idrija Mesto	Idrija Mesto	46,00211	14,02451
Idrija Topilnica	Idrija Topilnica	46,00762	14,03137
Pokljuka (Transplanted lichens)	Pokljuka (Transplanted lichens)	46,34536	13, 95298

Pokljuka 1 (insitu)	Pokljuka 1 (insitu)	46,34285	13,9547
Pokljuka 2 (insitu)	Pokljuka 2 (insitu)	46,34536	13,95298
Pokljuka 3 (insitu)	Pokljuka 3 (insitu)	46,3483	13,92499
Pokljuka 4 (insitu)	Pokljuka 4 (insitu)	46,34601	13,92433
Pokljuka 5 (insitu)	Pokljuka 5 (insitu)	46,32796	13,97818
Pokljuka 6 (insitu)	Pokljuka 6 (insitu)	46,33877	13,96233

2.2 Hg Measurements in air

Active Hg measurement was performed using different analytical systems provided by Tekran Corporation and Lumex. The Tekran instrument uses the pre-concentration of mercury on sorbent cartridges and then carries out the analysis with cold vapor atomic fluorescence spectroscopy (CVAFS), while the Lumex stands out for the direct measurement of elemental mercury in the air using cold vapor Zeeman atomic absorption spectroscopy (CVAAS).

2.2.1 Gaseous elemental Hg using AFS (Tekran)

Tekran system

Automated Hg speciation analyzer systems were used during the field measurement study (see in Figure 3.8). The analyzer system Tekran Model 2537B is used to simultaneously monitor GEM in ambient air (Tekran, 2001). The instruments were mounted closely at one location, North-Eastern part of the cement plant in Vodarna at a distance of about 1000 m away from the cement plant and an elevation of 70 metres above ground level. The Tekran Hg Vapor Analyzer (Model 2537B) provides continuous analysis of gaseous Hg in the air at sub-nanogram per cubic meter levels. The sample air stream is passed through cartridges containing ultra-pure, solid gold adsorbent media where the vapor phase Hg is collected. The amalgamated Hg is then thermally desorbed and detected in an integrated CVAFS detector. The instrument utilizes two gold cartridges in parallel, with alternating operation modes (sampling and desorbing - analyzing) usually on a predefined time base of 5-minute cycles. A 47 mm diameter Teflon pre-filter, placed

downstream of the sampling line, protects the sampling cartridges against contamination by particulate matter. The instrument is equipped with an internal mercury permeation source, providing a stable, repeatable alternative to calibration by manual injection. A stable permeation rate is ensured by the presence of a temperature-controlled aluminum block that contains the Hg permeation chamber and maintains its temperature within 0.05 °C of the set-point (between 45 to 75 °C, usually 50 °C). The sampling airflow through the speciation system was set to 1 L/min and 300 sec of sampling time, with a total volume of 5 liters passing through the gold cartridges. Calibration results and measured data were recorded by a laptop computer using Tekran provided software. All measurements were blank corrected. The precision of the Tekran 2537B is 2 % with a detection limit of 0.5 ng/m³ (Tekran, 2001).

2.2.1.1 Calibration and quality control

Calibration of Hg measuring instruments is important as it assures the accuracy and precision of measurements in a research study. Commercial devices designed for monitoring Hg in the air have their own methods of calibrations for measuring Hg.

Calibration and quality control in the Tekran system

In order to prevent contamination and eliminate any possibility of oxidation on the permeation tube surface, only a dry inert gas is used to provide a continuous purge flow. A capillary restriction, fed by the pressure regulator provides this constant flow. The quality control protocol in the laboratory and the field included overall control of the sampling/analysis measurements. No contamination was expected from the Hg analyzer Tekran 2537B because it is an automated device working within a closed and clean environment. The Tekran 2537B detector was calibrated by inbuilt calibration using a permeation source, providing 105.5 pg of Hg⁰ to gold traps. Recalibration was set to every 24 hours, occurring near midnight. For checking of internal permeation source, manual calibration was performed using injections of a known amount of Hg⁰ from bell-jar (Tekran 2505) using Hamilton 25 µL gas-tight microsyringe. The injected amount of Hg was calculated using the Dumarey equation. During the manual calibration, the mass and volume of the Hg⁰ to be calculated for calibration, with the known syringe set point, the syringe is injected into the 2505 containing mercury and the knob used to adjust the calculated (25 ng/m³) amount of mercury needed. Septum 2505 is replaced before the injection and Tekran 2505 also replaced after injection to avoid contamination in both

cases, both septums are then cleaned. The calibration time varies but usually between 120 – 300 seconds. Results for one month of instrument calibrations are presented in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7: Results from the calibration of the Tekran instrument measured from December 1, 2019 to January, 2020.

Figure 3.8: Sampling unit of the Tekran air Hg speciation system and Sir Galahad II sampling air inlet at the Vodarna site.

2.2.2 Gaseous elemental Hg measurements using Lumex

GEM concentrations in air were measured at all sampling locations using the Lumex RA-915M Hg detector (Lumex, St. Petersburg, Russia). The LUMEX Mercury Analyzer is a portable multifunctional atomic absorption spectrometer with Zeeman background correction, which eliminates the effect of interfering impurities. It is the only high sensitivity and selectivity instrument that does not require gold amalgam pre-concentration and subsequent regeneration steps. This enables the user to conduct real-time monitoring and detection of Hg in the air directly with an ultra-low detection limit. This instrument has a built-in performance verification test cell and auto-zero function, for rapid and simple verification of calibration. Typically, certified reference materials (CRMs) can be used for accurate calibrations, obtaining calibration curves. The content of Hg in the sample is determined from the calibration curve of the absolute amount of Hg (ng) versus the integrated analytical signal.

The RA-915 M is a real-time Hg detector that employs a Zeeman atomic absorption spectrometry using high frequency modulated light polarisation (ZAAS-HFM). The Lumex RA-915 M has a time resolution of 1 s which allows average concentrations to be computed internally, and this gives a 1 ng m^{-3} limit of detection (LOD) at 1 s time resolution (Sholupov et al., 2004). Hg concentrations in air were recorded on a laptop

computer and at selected locations and different seasons. GEM concentrations were measured 1.5 m above the road surface.

2.2.3 Biomonitoring

Biomonitoring using lichens is a conventional technique that has been used in many studies for determining atmospheric Hg concentration. Lichens are proven to be the most prominent, relevant and cost-effective approach and are suitable for long term measurement of Hg in air. In this study, two species of lichens were used for the study; insitu lichen species *Punctelia subrudecta* and *Flavoparmelia caperata* and transplanted lichens *Hypogymnia physodes*.

2.2.3.1 Sampling of in-situ lichens

In situ lichens in Figure 3.9 were sampled from all locations where transplanted lichens were exposed. For the in-situ lichens, species of *Punctelia subrudecta* and *Flavoparmelia caperata* were collected from the same locations where the exposed lichen bags were placed. The preparation of in-situ lichens for analysis was performed the same way as for the transplanted lichens. The concentration of Hg in lichens was determined for each sampling period and every exposed bag. From each bag, Hg was determined in duplicates to check the homogeneity of the sample. Lichen samples were placed in paper bags and transported to the laboratory for analysis. The same species has been used in many studies on atmospheric Hg concentrations in different parts of the world (Lupsina et al., 1992; Jeran, et al., 1996, 2002, 2007; Horvat et al., 2000).

Figure 3.9: In-situ lichens (*Punctelia subrudecta* and *Flavoparmelia*) caperata collected at Anhovo site.

2.2.3.2 Transplantation of lichens

For transplanted lichens, *Hypogymnia physodes* lichen was selected, as it is considered to be one of the most studied lichens in relation to various biomonitoring studies (in Figure 3.10a and b). Large amounts of lichen thalli (undifferentiated vegetative tissues) were collected from the Pokljuka plateau (1200 m above sea level), which is considered as a remote site far from any influence of anthropogenic activities. The collection of lichen thalli was performed during January 2020. The collected material was stored in paper bags. After cleaning the lichens from excess wood material, lichens were packed in nylon net bags, weighing approximately 4 – 5 g.

Lichen bags were usually placed on branches of various trees at the height of 1.5 – 2 m above ground. For each exposure period, two to three bags with lichens were prepared. After the selected exposure time, transplanted lichen bags were brought to the laboratory and cleaned from the dead parts and wood.

Figure 3.10: Exposure of *Hypogymnia physodes* lichens at Vodarna (A) and Morsko (B) sites.

2.2.3.3 Lichens pretreatment for Hg analysis

The standard operating procedures for determining total Hg in soil, sediments and organic materials in several studies (Akagi, et al., 1995; Horvat et al., 1997; Logar et al., 2001; Marcio et al., 2019) were used during the laboratory preparation and analysis phase. Laboratory preparatory procedures protocols in lichens preparation were done in two phases. From collected in situ or transplanted lichen samples any visible foreign organic and inorganic materials such as pieces of bark, trapped plastics, insects etc., were removed with pincers. Only healthy and undamaged thalli were processed by drying using lyophilizator at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under the vacuum of 0.28 mbar (Christ; Martin Christ Gefriertrocknungsanlagen, Germany), and ground and homogenized following immersion in liquid nitrogen.

2.2.3.4 Total Hg determination in lichens

Due to the possibility that lichens might have adsorbed some silicon-containing inorganic material into their structure during their exposure, the concentration of Hg in lichens was determined using the method for the determination of Hg in inorganic matrices. The analysis was performed at the JSI laboratory using the method described in detail below. Prior to analysis, all labware was thoroughly cleaned. Teflon vessels were soaked overnight in a soap solution (Micro solution, 2 % in tap water), rinsed thoroughly with tap water and then with Milli-Q water, and placed in 50 % (v/v) concentrated HNO₃ solution and heated at 100 °C for 2 days. Following the heating, vessels were rinsed thoroughly with Milli-Q water and transferred into 10 % (v/v) concentrated HCl solution for one day at room temperature. Teflon vessels were then rinsed thoroughly with Milli-Q water and allowed to dry at 60 °C in a ventilated oven.

Before the sample digestion, vials containing the samples were shaken for about 2 min, for homogenization. About 0.2 g of dry sample was weighted in Teflon vials (25 mL), which was then wetted with 1 mL of Milli-Q water. 5 mL of a mixture of concentrated HNO₃/HF (2:1) mixture and 1 mL of concentrated HCl was then slowly added to the sample. Vessels were then capped and left to stand for at least 1 hour at room temperature. If the reaction became very strong, the vessel was left at room temperature overnight before heating. Teflon vessels were then placed into an aluminum block on a hot plate at 100 °C and left overnight for digestion. Samples were then cooled to room temperature before opening the tubes. The content of the Teflon vessels was diluted with 5 % H₃BO₃ solution (w/v) to the mark. The vessels were then closed and shaken prior to analysis. Samples prepared in this manner can be kept for a few days before analysis if stored in the refrigerator (+4 °C).

At least two reagent blanks were prepared for each batch of analysis. They were prepared similarly as samples, except that no sample was added to the digestion vessel. At least one certified reference material was used and prepared in triplicate for each batch of analysis. These digestions are prepared similarly as for samples. Certified reference material should be of similar composition and concentration of Hg as samples. The chosen certified reference material was IAEA-336 (lichens) whose certified concentration of total mercury is 0.2 µg/g dry weight, with a 95 % confidence interval of 0.16 – 0.24 µg/g dry weight.

The concentration of Hg in digested samples was determined using the atomic absorbance spectrometer – Model Hg-201 Semi-automated Mercury Analyzer (Sanso Seisakusho Co. Ltd., Tokyo, Japan). A known volume of the blank solution, standard solution, or the sample solution was placed in the reaction vessel of the mercury analyser system and diluted with Milli-Q water up to 5 mL. Then 1 mL of 10% SnCl₂ (w/v) in 10% HCl (v/v) solution was also added with the accessory dispenser. The reaction mixture was purged and the generated elemental mercury vapours circulated through the 4-way valve between the reaction vessel and the acidic gas trap for 30 seconds in order to homogenize the concentration in the gas phase. Concurrently, the acidic gas generated from the solution was trapped in the alkaline solution. After 30 seconds, the 4-way valve turned automatically by 90°, allowing the introduction of acid-free mercury vapor into the photo-absorption cell for the measurement of the absorbance at 254 nm.

The concentration of Hg in lichen samples was calculated from the obtained absorbance signals of the sample and standard solution, after correction for the corresponding blank signal. The final result is reported on a dry weight basis after separate determination of the residual water content in each lichen sample.

2.2.3.5 Quality control

The quality of the THg analysis of the lichen samples was performed using IAEA-336 as certified reference material. These digestions are prepared similarly to samples. The repeatability of measurements was about 2 – 5 %. Certified reference material is of similar composition and concentration of Hg as samples. The chosen certified reference material was IAEA-336 (lichens) whose certified concentration of THg is 0.2 µg/g dry weight, with a 95 % confidence interval of 0.16 – 0.24 µg/g dry weight. Four samples of IAEA-336 were prepared with a reasonable dilution factor (dilution of 3 – 5 times) and these samples were then analyzed. Logar et al., (2001) studies revealed the accuracy and reliability of this method using diss-MeHg analysis in international intercomparison studies. The limit of detection (LOD) was 0.02 ng/L, computation of the LOD was achieved from the standard deviation of four blank solutions. Results from the measurements using the reference materials as quality control are illustrated in Table 3.2. Reasons for the difference in results of measured using the same sample masses are best attributed to systematic and human errors.

Table 3.2. THg concentrations (ng/g) measured from the reference material IAEA-336 using the atomic absorbance spectrometer – Model Hg-201 Semi-automated Mercury Analyzer

Sample masses (g)	THg conc. (ng/g)	Standard peak (mm)	Average THg conc. (ng/g)	StDev
0.2305	164	38.33	168	5.83
0.2022	173			
0.2085	173			
0.2067	162			
0.2305	154	38.83	157	5.42
0.2022	162			
0.2085	162			
0.2067	151			

2.3 Hg Emissions and Meteorological Data

Cement plant Hg emissions were measured in the plant chimney using the method of continuous Hg monitoring system (SICK), an atomic absorption spectrometer with Zeeman background correction, which eliminates the effect of interfering impurities. Continuous monitoring of Hg emissions from cement plants into the surroundings is a technological approach implemented from the European Union and adopted by member countries as a means of controlling and curbing the quantity of Hg which escape from cement facilities into the environment. However, this project used available emission data from the MERCOX project through which the technology was installed in the plant. The amount of Hg released from the cement plant into the environment play a crucial role in influencing policies aim at protecting the environment and the lives of organisms. The system used in this exercise measures continuous Hg emission levels in thirty-minute interval. The system was installed in July 2020, so data are available only after this period.

The main meteorological data such as ambient air temperature, pressure, humidity, wind speed and direction, precipitation, etc. were measured at the Bilje observing station by ARSO (Slovenian Environmental Agency) and at the Vodarna sampling site by Anhovo cement plant.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Hg Emission from the Cement Plant in Anhovo

Figure 2.1 and 2.2 presents a 30-minute interval of continuous Hg mass (g/h) and concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) emitted from the cement plant. Six months of data were available from the cement facility. The emitted mass flow from the facility was in the range from 0.16 g – 14.3 g/h. The average output of Hg emitted from the cement facility is illustrated in Table 2.1. The emitted mass flow range in comparison is significantly higher (about 1 – 2 fold, that is from 0.16 – 14.3 g/h) than the previous study reported by Ljubič-Mlakar et al., 2010, 2011 (between 0.1 and 2.4 g/h). It is difficult to estimate the annual Hg mass output from the plant due to limited data available, however, the estimated total Hg mass output for the one year is approximately 30 kg. The yearly Hg mass output measured in this study is higher than the estimated total Hg mass output from the previous study performed by Ljubič-Mlakar et al., (2010), 10 kg representing about one-third of the annual input. The facility has bag filters installed which are efficient in reducing dust. The plant emits 0.1 – 0.25 kg/h of dust. Gaseous Hg represents the majority of emitted Hg with 99.7 %, and particulate bound Hg represents 0.3 %. Hg species emitted during the process are variable due to the difference in the operational regime. For instance, when the system is operated in the so-called direct mode, Hg^{2+} is much higher (up to 81 %) than in the combined mode (up to 51%) (Ljubič-Mlakar, 2011). Hg concentration in flue gases ranges from 1.3 – 98.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Figure 2.1). The estimated average Hg concentration in the facility for the entire six months is 26.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Masses of other chemical compounds in flue gases are presented in Table 2.2.

Table 2.1: Average Hg mass emitted (g/h) from the cement facility.

Months	Average Hg mass emitted (g/h)
July	4.84 ± 1.69
August	4.10 ± 1.20
September	3.55 ± 1.67
October	3.50 ± 1.10
November	3.54 ± 1.10
December	3.70 ± 1.82

Table 2.2: Emitted mass of other gases present in flue gases of the cement plant.

Compounds	Mass range (kg/h)
NO ₂	18 – 156
SO ₂	0.05 – 13.4
CO	11 – 187
O ₂	0.15 – 10

Figure 2.1: Hg emissions (g/h) from the cement operational facility measured at 30 minute intervals.

Figure 2.2: Hg concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) in flue gases in the cement plant Anhovo measured at 30-minute interval

3.2 Gaseous elemental Hg in air

The statistical results of GEM in air collected during the period using the Tekran detectors are shown in Table 2.3. GEM concentrations in air at Vodarna were computed for average, geometric mean and standard deviations monthly for twelve months, and the results were compared as shown in Table 4.3. The highest monthly mean GEM concentrations were observed in December 2019 with a value of $6.21 \pm 2.84 \text{ ng/m}^3$ (SD included in all measurements) and the lowest value of $1.56 \pm 0.55 \text{ ng/m}^3$ was recorded in December 2020.

Table 2.3: Average monthly GEM concentrations computed statistically by the Tekran speciation system in Vodarna. SD indicates standard deviation of all measurements performed during the corresponding month.

Months	Instruments	Geometric mean	Average	SD
Dec-19	Tekran	5.62	6.21	2.84
Jan-20	Tekran	2.6	2.57	1.38
Feb-20	Tekran	2.5	2.83	1.83
Mar-20	Tekran	2.42	2.71	1.28
Apr-20	Tekran	3.02	2.45	1.25
May-20	Tekran	2.12	2.27	1.27
Jun-20	Tekran	*	*	*
Jul-20	Tekran	*	*	*
Aug-20	Tekran	*	*	*
Sep-20	Tekran	*	*	*
Oct-20	Tekran	2.05	2.19	0.75
Nov-20	Tekran	1.97	2.06	0.73
Dec-20	Tekran	1.60	1.56	0.55
Jan-21	Tekran	1.78	1.81	0.32

*no measurements were recorded.

GEM in air was measured one year from December 6, 2019 – December 20, 2020. Inevitable interruptions for certain events were encountered due to the instrument maintenance and functioning. The longest events where data could not be retrieved include: (1) 27 December, 2019, 9:44 – 3 January, 2020, 10:44; (2) 1 – 5 March, 2020,

17:39:44 – 12:14; (3) 26 April – 6 May 2020, 13:39 –11:39; (4) 29 May, – 9 September, 2020, 0:4:42 – 9:54:42 (5) 18 November – 30 November, 2020, 0:4:42 –23:59:42. The summer period was the most affected of all the seasons, representing about 80 – 90 % of the data loss.

The 5-minute intervals of GEM concentrations in air over the entire sampling period are demonstrated in Figure 4.3a. The lowest GEM value recorded is 0.5 ng/m^3 and the highest value is 29.5 ng/m^3 . Most of the high GEM peaks were detected during the daytime, which is evident in the cement facility operating within this period. The suspension of the facility over a 14-day period (April 24 – May 4, 2020) recorded low peaks as shown in Figures 2.3b and 2.3c. A comparison of the seasonality of measurements in Figure 2.3a shows the highest spikes recorded between December 2019 – January 2020. A similar trend of high spikes was observed from March 17 – April 5, 2020, 18 – 23 May 2020. Unfortunately, between May to August, measurements for GEM could not be established and therefore, it was not possible to present judgement within that period.

Figure 2.3: (A) Continuous measurements of GEM (in ng/m³) in air using the Tekran speciation detector for one year (December 6, 2019 – December 20, 2020). (B) Continuous time series measurements of GEM (ng/m³) in air in April, 2020, and (C) time series measurement at the period when the cement facility was not in operation (April 24 – May 4, 2020).

3.2.1 Temporal variations of GEM

Spring analysis – weekly variations

A detailed comparative weekly assessment of GEM concentrations and the wind directions are shown in Figures 2.4, 2.5, 2.6 and 2.7. An assessment was made for April 2020, as most GEM data were available for this month. Each week in April GEM concentrations were analyzed and compared to prevailing wind direction or wind direction relative frequency (in %). Information on wind direction was acquired from the meteorological station in Vodarna operated by the cement plant.

The highest GEM values were recorded in Week 1 (1 to 7 April 2020) on April 4, 2020 (10.9 ng/m³). The GEM in Week 1 recorded higher concentrations compared to the GEM in Week 2 (8. to 14. April 2020), Week 3 (15 to 21 April 2020) and Week 4 (22 to 28 April 2020)(Figures 4.4 to 4.7). Higher GEM peaks in Week 1 compared to other three weeks in April were accompanied by prevailing and dominant wind during the week blowing in the direction from ENE (RF up to 28.6 %)(Figure 2.4). However, in Week 2 (Figure 2.5), a greater proportion of winds are in directions from E (RF up to 33.3 %) and ESE (RF up to 16.6 %) resulting in lower GEM concentrations at Vodarna in Week 1. In Weeks 2 and 3 prevailing wind direction is E to W, showing lower GEM concentrations than in Week 1, but significantly higher than in Week 4, when prevailing wind direction was in the opposite direction than chimney, from SW to NE. Lower GEM peaks recorded in week 4 compared to week 1, week 2, and week 3 and wind directions blowing away from the sampling station coincided with the ten-day non-operational regime of the cement facility (April 24 – May 4, 2020).

Figure 2.4: Prevailing wind direction expressed as wind direction relative frequency in comparison to GEM concentrations at Vodarna in the week between 1 to 7 April 2020 (Week 1).

Figure 3.5: Prevailing wind direction expressed as wind direction relative frequency in comparison to GEM concentrations at Vodarna in the week between 8 to 14 April 2020 (Week 2).

Figure 2.6: Prevailing wind direction expressed as wind direction relative frequency in comparison to GEM concentrations at Vodarna in the week between 15 to 21 April 2020 (Week 3).

Figure 2.7: Prevailing wind direction expressed as wind direction relative frequency in comparison to GEM concentrations at Vodarna in the week between 22 to 28 April 2020 (Week 4).

However, GEM concentrations measured at Vodarna in April show a clear correlation with prevailing wind direction, resulting in high GEM peaks when the wind is blowing directly from the cement plant chimney to Vodarna (NE to SW), and in lower GEM events when wind is blowing in opposite direction, from SW to NE.

To confirm the influence of wind and Cement Plant operation on GEM concentrations measured at Vodarna, fall analysis of daily data was performed as described below.

Fall analysis – daily variations

With the established evidence of winds in the direction of the sampling station resulting in high GEM peaks in the weekly analysis, we determined the influence of the influx of Hg emitted from the cement facility and the prevailing and dominant winds blowing in directions from the chimney to Vodarna on the GEM concentrations. Daily correlations between cement plant Hg emissions, wind direction and GEM concentrations, obtained on 12 October 2020 are presented in Figure 2.8. High GEM peaks events were recorded from 13:30 to 18:15 on a particular day. The rise of GEM peaks during the period

coincided with wind directions blowing from E (RF up to 48 %), ENE (RF up to 26 %), NE (RF up to 19 %) and NNE (RF up to 7 %). The rise of GEM concentrations and the dominant wind directions (E, ENE, NE and NNE) blowing toward Vodarna coincided with the period where high Hg peaks were emitted from the cement facility from 10:30 to 13:00. In addition, low GEM concentrations closely align with the time when lower Hg emissions from the cement were recorded. It can be concluded that low Hg emissions from the production facility resulted in low GEM concentrations measured during the period (12:39 – 11:34 and 7:39 – 11:54) despite a majority of the winds being directed toward the sampling site. Also, high GEM concentrations measured during the period 13:30 to 18:15 corresponds to high Hg emissions from the cement plant and wind direction, blowing from NE towards SW as shown in Figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8: Daily Hg emissions from the Anhovo cement plant in correlation with prevailing wind direction and ambient GEM concentrations measured at Vodarna. Data were recorded on 12 October 2020.

3.3 Gaseous Elemental Hg Concentrations in Air Measured by Lumex

Active daily measurements of air GEM concentrations were recorded at different seasons at all locations where lichens were exposed, using Lumex RA-915M. The measurements were performed at selected locations within the former Hg mine (Idrija Topilnica, Idrija Spodnja and Idrija Uprava) and stations in proximity to the cement plant (Vodarna, Morsko, Anhovo and Rocinj). Higher GEM values were recorded in Idrija Topilnica (near the smeltery plant) compared to Idrija Uprava, Spodnja Idrija and locations near the cement plant. The highest GEM values of 78.2, 55.8, and 64.2 ng/m³ were recorded for July 7, August 14, and October 16, 2020 in Idrija Topilnica, respectively. These measurements coincided with an increase in daily temperatures recorded during the period. Average daily temperatures include; 22.1 °C, 23 °C and 10.6 °C for July 7, August 14, and October 16 respectively. However, November 16 and December 1 in Idrija Topilnica recorded a decrease in temperatures with values of 5.1 and 2.3 °C respectively. During that period, a decrease in GEM values (13.9 and 14.6 ng/m³) was recorded. Location Idrija Uprava showed lower GEM concentrations compared to location Topilnica. We presume that the GEM concentrations at Idrija locations are influenced by meteorological parameters such as temperature, air pressure and humidity, wind speed, wind direction, etc.

In general, Idrija Topilnica, which is closer to the former smeltery plant, showed higher GEM concentrations compared to areas within the Idrija town (Idrija Uprava and Spodnja Idrija). It is evident that the former smeltery sites contribute significantly to Hg evasion and distribution within the Idrija vicinity. Variations of GEM values recorded during the period for all stations are related to the emission sources, meteorology and atmospheric oxidant levels (Poissant and Hoenninger 2004). Similar trends of higher Hg concentrations in air recorded in the smeltery site and within the Idrija town were reported in other studies (Kotnik et al., 2005; Kocman et al., 2010).

Figure 2.9: Comparison of average GEM concentrations (ng/m^3) measured at selected locations around the cement facility in Anhovo and in Idrija.

3.4 Comparison of the Trend of Hg Concentrations in Air in Idrija

The past and present datasets from two locations in Idrija (near the former smeltery plant and the Idrija town, Idrija Topilnica, and Idrija Uprava, respectively) were used to compare the trend of atmospheric Hg concentrations in more than 50 years. Higher Hg concentration levels were recorded near the former smeltery than in Idrija. In the early and mid-1970s, Kosta et al., (1974) reported Hg concentration levels with a value of over $20\,000\ \text{ng}/\text{m}^3$. Increased Hg concentrations recorded during early and mid-1970s correspond to the period of high Hg production (Hg mining activities) according to the study. The study recorded elevated Hg levels within Idrija, with a value of about $6\,000\ \text{ng}/\text{m}^3$ (see in Figure 2.10). In the late 1970s and 1980s, Hg concentrations in air in Idrija decreased substantially to a value below $1\,000$, and $10\,000\ \text{ng}/\text{m}^3$ near the smeltery site. In 1995, Hg concentrations in Idrija increased to a value of above $1\,000\ \text{ng}/\text{m}^3$ due to the last smelting of heavily Hg contaminated materials. Gosar et al., (1997) and Gnamuš et al., (2000) reported a decrease in Hg concentrations compared to the study by Kosta et al. (1974) with values in the range from $45 - 10\ \text{ng}/\text{m}^3$ within Idrija and Hg concentration value above $1\,000\ \text{ng}/\text{m}^3$ near the smelting plant. A recent study performed by Kotnik et

al. (2005) revealed Hg air concentrations of 10 ng/m³ in Idrija town and 1 264 ng/m³ near the smeltery site. The present study (in 2020) revealed a slight decrease in Hg concentration levels compared to the study reported by Kotnik et al. (2005) with average Hg air concentrations of 4 ng/m³ within the Idrija, and 14 ng/m³ near the smeltery site. The general trend of Hg in air levels consistently decreases in the town and at the smeltery site. The continuous decrease of Hg concentrations in air in Idrija town and the smeltery site from 1997 – 2020 (Figure 2.10) is related to the impact of the natural recovery and the non-operational period of the mine (in 1995 – 2020). Also, the former smeltery sites showed higher air Hg concentrations compared to Idrija which correlates with the past trend.

Figure 2.10: Average Hg concentrations (ng/m³) in air over Idrija since 1970 (past data from Kotnik et al., 2005, and the present study).

3.5 Biomonitoring of Hg in Air by Epiphytic Lichens

3.5.1 THg in in situ lichens

The sampling locations are in three groups: the first group consists of areas within the vicinity of the former Hg mine (Spodnja Idrija, Idrija Uprava and Idrija Topilnica), the second group involves in situ lichens within the vicinity of the cement production facility (Vodarna, Rocinj, Morsko and Anhovo) and lastly, in situ lichens in the pristine

environment of Pokljuka as a reference. Relatively higher THg concentrations in air were recorded in locations closer to the former Hg mine. Idrija Topilnica (near the smeltery plant) recorded the highest value (up to 6 620 ng/g). Lichens collected in Spodnja Idrija and Idrija Uprava (located in Idrija) showed average THg concentrations of 547 and 1171 ng/g respectively. Within the vicinity of the cement production facility, THg concentrations were lower compared to values recorded in Idrija (up to 231 ng/g in Vodarna). However, values recorded in the vicinity of the cement facility are in close agreement (in the range from 170 – 262 ng/g) to the THg concentrations recorded in Pokljuka 1, 2, 3,4 and 5. The higher values of THg recorded in Idrija Topilnica compared with other 11 locations are a result of the proximity of the location to the former smeltery plant. Increased values recorded in Idrija Topilnica and Idrija Uprava and Spodnja Idrija compared to the locations at the cement facility and reference (Pokljuka) are due to factors such as the distances from the sources (smeltery site) to the sampling locations, age of the in situ lichens, and local variability. Figure 2.11 represents THg concentration in in situ lichens at locations included in this study.

Figure 2.11: THg concentration (ng/g, dry weight) in in situ lichens.

3.5.2 THg in transplanted lichens

Figure 2.12 and Figure 2.13 presents the results of the concentration of THg in transplanted lichen *H. physodes*. The concentrations of THg of all selected locations were measured after 3 and 6 months of transplanted lichens exposure. Evidently, for the 3-month measurements, THg concentrations in the vicinity of the cement facility in Anhovo were generally lower (up to 227 ± 12.7 ng/g) than THg concentrations recorded in Idrija, with THg values up to 385 ± 34.9 ng/g.

For the 6 months dataset, THg concentrations recorded an increase in values compared to those measured after 3 months of lichens exposure. Idrija Topilnica recorded higher THg enrichment (THg concentration up to 871 ± 103 ng/g). Surprisingly, for measurements recorded in 3 months, an increase in the value of THg concentrations is recorded in Vodarna and is comparable to Spodnja Idrija. The reason for the increase in the value of THg in Vodarna (up to 211 ng/g) compared to Spodnja Idrija (up to 205 ng/g) is attributed to the local transports of THg from nearby sources. It is also interesting to compare THg in lichens that were exposed under the covered roof with those in lichens exposed by hanging on trees in the open. At the Anhovo station, there is no clear trend; for lichens exposed for three months, THg is greater in lichens exposed under the covered roof than in those exposed freely on trees, while for the exposure period of six months, the situation is reversed. However, all these values were relatively low and highly variable. On the contrary, at Idrija Uprava there is a clear trend. For both exposure times, THg was always greater in lichens exposed freely hanging on trees in the open. This might be due to the absorption of Hg from wet or dry deposition. As covered lichens are not exposed to rain, it is expected that they would not accumulate Hg from rain, while those that are freely hanging on trees might be able to obtain this additional source of Hg. However, this can be further tested using the stable isotope approach. Due to these differences in THg concentrations, lichen samples that were exposed under the covered roof were not included in the regression analyses. Furthermore, THg in situ lichens have higher values than in the transplanted lichens collected at the beginning of the exposure period, which could be due to the exposure and levels of uptake of THg in lichens, age of the lichen and its physiological conditions or some past events (Horvat et al., 2000).

Figure 2.12: THg concentration (ng/g, dry weight) in transplanted lichens exposed for 3 months.

Figure 2.13: THg concentration (ng/g, dry weight) in transplanted lichens exposed for 6 months.

3.5.3 Comparison of active air measurement with biomonitoring method

To evaluate whether lichens provide a good estimate for Hg concentrations in air, the results for THg concentration in lichens were compared with measurements recorded using the Lumex detector. Statistical analysis with the linear regression approach was used for the dataset from the in situ and transplanted lichens. As a result of high concentration differences between measurements closer to the contaminated sites (Idrija Uprava, Topilnica Idrija and Spodnja Idrija) and non-contaminated sites (Anhovo, Morsko, Rocinj and Vodarna), the geometric mean was used instead of the arithmetic mean for the active air measurements. Figure 2.14 expresses the correlation between THg in transplanted lichens for three months and active air measurement.

From the diagram for three months, an increase in Hg^0 concentration in air by 1 ng/m^3 corresponds to the increase of 15.0 ng/g of total Hg in transplanted lichens following the exposure time of three months. Although this value could be taken into account as a sort of ‘calibration’ of transplanted lichens for future determination of Hg^0 in the air, it is necessary to compare this value with those obtained after six months of exposure. As lichens are living organisms, their ability to absorb Hg from the air is not a chemical

process, but rather a biological and biochemical process. Therefore, the determination of the relation between Hg in lichens and the air might not be an easy task due to variations that might occur due to lichens growth, biochemistry, and other parameters unrelated to Hg^0 concentrations in the air. Furthermore, it can be seen that the amount of Hg in transplanted lichens is quite variable for samples taken at five stations where the average Hg^0 concentration in the air is about 1.5 ng/m^3 . Therefore, we compared this regression analysis with the corresponding one obtained for the exposure time of six months (Figure 2.15).

Figure 2.14: Relation between the amount of total Hg (ng/g) in transplanted lichens following the exposure time of three months and the mean Hg^0 concentration (ng/m^3) in the air at selected stations.

In Figure 2.15, it can be estimated that the increase of 1 ng/m^3 of Hg^0 in the air corresponds to the increase of 51.7 ng/g of total Hg in transplanted lichens following the exposure time of six months. When comparing with the exposure of three months, it is evident that the exposure of six months provides a much better linear correlation between total Hg in transplanted lichens and Hg^0 concentration in the air ($r^2 = 0.992$). Contrary to

large variations in THg in lichen samples taken at five stations where the average Hg^0 concentration in the air is about 1.5 ng/m^3 during the exposure of three months (Figure 2.14), the corresponding samples generally show a slight increase in THg concentrations following the exposure of six months. Therefore, longer exposure time seems to improve the estimation of Hg^0 in the air at lower concentration levels when using transplanted lichens.

Figure 2.15: Relation between the amount of total Hg (ng/g) in transplanted lichens following the exposure time of six months and the mean Hg^0 concentration (ng/m^3) in the air at selected stations.

It is interesting to compare the slopes of the regression analysis for three and six months of exposure. Even though the exposure time is two times longer, the corresponding slope for six months of exposure is approximately 3.5-fold greater than that for three months of exposure. This might be attributed to the biological processes related to Hg uptake by lichens. When lichens were transplanted, they might have experienced physiological stress that influenced their metabolism and biochemical processes. Lichens might have required a certain time to accustom themselves to the new environment in which they were exposed. Furthermore, the lichens were transplanted in January and the first exposure period of three months corresponds to winter conditions, when all biological processes are slower in general. This might be the reason why the uptake of Hg^0 from the air might have been accelerated during the second exposure period which was during both winter and spring (six months of exposure). However, this difference in non-linear

response during different exposure periods indicates that the ‘calibration’ of lichens cannot be generalized. The determination of the regression slope for the determination of unknown Hg^0 concentrations in the air based on the exposure of transplanted lichens must be performed concurrently with the exposure of these lichens. In addition, the conditions should be as identical as possible, including temperature, humidity, lichen species, etc. The slope of regression analysis between the amount of total Hg in transplanted lichens following the exposure time of six months and the mean Hg^0 concentration in the air at selected stations (Figure 2.15) were compared with other literature values. Figure 2.16 presents the regression correlation between a) mercury concentrations in transplanted *H. physodes* at Molve (natural gas treatment facility – MOL, CPS) and Idrija ((Horvat et al., 2000); black, rectangular symbols) and b) *P. furfuracea* around the cement plant Anhovo ((Mlakar et al., 2011); open round symbols) after 6 months of exposure vs. Hg^0 in air. It is important to note that this study found linear dependence between THg in lichens and Hg^0 in air, while the correlation in Figure 2.16 is based on a log-log scale. For comparison, we converted our data to log-log scale, even though the linearity was considerably reduced ($r^2 = 0.924$). We obtained the following relation for the exposure time of six months in the present study: $\log [\text{Hg}^0 (\text{ng m}^{-3})] = 1.65 \times \log [\text{THg in lichens (ng g}^{-1} \text{ d.w.)}] - 3.65$. For the literature data, we calculated the correlation and found that $\log [\text{Hg}^0 (\text{ng m}^{-3})] = 1.74 \times \log [\text{THg in lichens (ng g}^{-1} \text{ d.w.)}] - 3.11$. Therefore, the regression slopes between the current and previous studies are similar indicating similar sorption mechanisms and processes of airborne mercury by lichens.

Figure 2.16: Comparison of correlation between a) mercury concentrations in transplanted *H. physodes* at Molve (natural gas treatment facility – MOL, CPS) and Idrija ((Horvat et al., 2000); black, rectangular symbols) and b) *P. furfuracea* around the cement plant Salanit-Anhovo ((Mlakar et al., 2011); open round symbols) after 6 months of exposure vs. Hg^0 in air.

To further test the applicability of lichens as a proxy for Hg^0 concentrations in the air, the amount of total Hg absorbed by in situ lichens was compared with Hg^0 concentration in air that was actively measured by the Lumex instrument. It was presumed that the concentration of Hg^0 in the air was more or less constant during the whole growth period of the collected lichens (data not available). The correlation between the amount of THg in situ lichens and the mean Hg^0 concentrations in the air is presented in Figure 2.17. Similar to transplanted lichens, it is evident that the THg concentrations in in-situ lichens show a nice linear correlation with Hg^0 concentration in the air ($r^2 = 0.992$). If we assume that the in situ lichens have accumulated the maximum possible amount of Hg^0 from the air, then the maximal change of Hg that lichen can accumulate when Hg^0 concentration increases by 1 ng/m^3 is 509 ng/g .

Figure 2.17: Relation between the amount of total Hg (ng/g) in in-situ lichens and the mean Hg^0 concentration (ng/m³) in the air at selected station.

Conclusions

Seasonal analysis of GEM concentrations measured using the Tekran analyzer at Vodarna combined with the Hg emissions from the facility showed a strong positive correlation, especially with wind directions playing a major influence in GEM peaks at the sampling location. Higher Hg emissions from the facility in addition to dominant wind directions toward the sampling station correspond to GEM recorded. Also, periods where the cement plant was operational resulted in higher peaks of GEM at Vodarna compared to the non-operational period of the cement facility.

Hg concentrations observed using Lumex RA-915M in the vicinity of the smeltery plants recorded higher values compared to values recorded at the cement plant and the reference (Pokljuka). Comparison of elevated Hg levels in air in Idrija (in the Idrija town and near the smeltery site) shows a decrease in the trend of Hg concentrations measured between 1970 – 2020.

Biomonitoring technique was implemented using transplanted lichens (*Hypogymnia physodes*), and in-situ lichens (*Punctelia subrudecta* and *Flavoparmelia caperata*). Results from both the in situ and transplanted lichens showed that lichens are very sensitive to air contamination and are known to accumulate compounds and elements in amounts that closely correlate with atmospheric levels. As it was seen in previous studies, concentrations of Hg in in-situ and transplanted lichens correlate well with air Hg concentrations. Longer time of lichens exposure has a positive correlation compared to short duration. This was concluded using a statistical t-test analysis for 3 and 6 months lichens sample measurements. From the analysis, there is an 85.68 % chance that there is a significant difference (confidence interval), but since the CI < 95%, it is very close. Biomonitoring using epiphytic lichens proved to be the most prominent, reliable and cost-effective method for long term monitoring of Hg in air. Comparison of the results of biomonitoring using lichens with air measurements showed a strong relationship (R^2 for 3 and 6 months measurements is 0.966 and 0.992). To ensure proper growth and development of transplanted lichens, and with that stable absorption of Hg from air, sampling and transplantation protocols should be developed

References

- Bahlmann, E., Ebinghaus, R., 2003. Process Studies on Mercury Fluxes Over Different Soils With a Laboratory Flux Measurement System (LFMS). 107. 102.
- Car, J., 1996. Mineralized rocks and ore residues in the Idrija region. Proceedings of the meeting of researchers on Idrija as a natural and anthropogenic laboratory/Mercury as a major pollutant, 10–15.
- Essa, M, H., Muazu, N, D., Lukman, S., Bukhari, A., 2015. Application of box-behnken design to hybrid electrokinetic-adsorption removal of mercury from contaminated saline-sodic clay Soil Sediment Contam., 24. 30-48.
- Gosar, M., Pirc, S., Bidovec, M., 1997a. Mercury in the IdrijaRiver sediments as a reflection of mining and smeltingactivities of the Idrija mercury mine. Journal of Geochem. Explor. 58 (2/3), 125–131.
- Gosar, M., Pirc, S., Šajn, R., Bidovec, M., Mashyanov, N, R., Sholupov, S., 1997b. Distribution of mercury in theatmosphere over Idrija, Slovenia. Environ. Geochemistry and Health 19 (3), 101–110.
- Grönlund, R., Edner, H., Svanberg, S., Kotnik, J., Horvat, M., 2005. Mercury emissions from the Idrija mercury mine measured by differential absorption lidar techniques and a point monitoring absorption spectrometer. Atmos. Environ. 39(22), 4067–4074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j>
- Gustin, M, S., Amos, H, M., Huang, J., Miller, M, B., Heidecorn, K., 2015. Measuring and modeling mercury in the atmosphere: a critical review. Atmos. Chem. Phys., 15, 5697–5713.
- Gustin, M, S., Biester, H., Kim, C, S., 2002. Investigation of the Light-enhance Emission of Hg from naturally enriched substrates. 36, 3254.
- Gustin, M, S., Stamenkovic, J., 2005. Effects of Watering and Soil and Soil Moisture on Mercury Emission from Soils. 76, 232.
- Han, C., Wang, H., Xie, F., Wang, W., Zhang, T., Dreisinger, D., 2019. Feasibility study on the use of thiosulfate to remediate mercury-contaminated soil. Environ. Technol., 40. 813-821.
- Horvat, M., Jeran, Z., Špiric, Z., Jacimovic, R., Miklavcic, V., 2000. Mercury and other elements in lichens near the INA Naftaplin gas treatment plant, Molve, Croatia. Environ. Monit. 2, 139–144.

- Horvat, M., Jereb, V., Fajon, V., Logar, M., Bonzongo, J. C., Faganeli, J., Hines, M. 2002. Mercury distribution in water, sediment and soil in the Idrija and Soc̑a river system. *Materials and Geoenvironment*, 48, 65–78.
- Horvat, M., Kocman, D., Pirrone, N., Cinnirella, S., 2011. Contribution of contaminated sites to the global mercury budget. <https://www.slideserve.com/nakia/contribution-of-contaminated-sites-to-the-global-mercury-budget>.
- Horvat, M., Kotnik, J., Logar, M., Fajon, V., Zvonaric, T., Pirrone, N., 2003. Speciation of mercury in surfaces and deep-sea water in the Mediterranean Sea. *Atmos. Environ.*, 37 (SUPPL.1). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1352-2310\(03\)00249-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1352-2310(03)00249-8).
- Horvat, M., Liang, L., Azemard, S., Mandic, V., Villeneuve, J. P., Coquery, M., 1997. Certification of total mercury and methylmercury concentrations in mussel homogenate (*Mytilus edulis*) reference material, IAEA-142. *Fresenius J Anal Chem* 358:411–418
- Jeran, Z., Jacimovic, R., Batic, F., Mavsar, R., 2002. Lichens as integrated air pollution monitors. *Environ. Pollut.* 120, 107–113.
- Jeran, Z., Jacimovic, R., Batic, F., Smodiš, B., Wolterbeek, H., 1996. Atmospheric heavy metal pollution in Slovenia derived from results for epiphytic lichens. *Fresenius. Analyt. Chem.* 354(5–6), 681–687.
- Jeran, Z., Mrak, T., Jaćimović, R., Batič, F., Kastelec, D., Mavsar, R., Simončič, P., 2007. Epiphytic lichens as biomonitors of atmospheric pollution in Slovenian forests, *Environmental Pollution*, Volume 146, 324-331, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j>
- Kocman, D., Horvat, M., 2011. Non-point source mercury emission from the Idrija Hg-mine region: GIS mercury emission model, *J. Environ. Mgmt*, 92, 2038-2046,
- Kocman, D., Horvat, M., Kotnik, J., 2004. Mercury fractionation in contaminated soils from the Idrija mercury mine region. *Journal of Environ. Monit.* 6, 696–703.
- Kocman, D., Horvat, M., Pirrone, N., Cinnirella, S., 2013. Contribution of contaminated sites to the global mercury budget. *Environ. Res.* 125, 160–170.
- Kocman, D., Vreča, P., Horvat, M., 2011. Atmospheric distribution and deposition of mercury in the Idrija mine region. *Environ. R.* 111, 1-9.
- Kosta, L., Byrne, A. R., Zelenko, V., Stegnar, P., Dermelj, M., Ravnik, V., 1974. Studies on uptake, distribution and transformations of mercury in living organisms in the Idrija region and comparative areas. *Vestnik slovenskega kemijskega društva* 21, 49–76.
- Kotnik, J., Horvat, M., Dizdarevič, T., 2005. Current and past mercury distribution in air over the Idrija Hg mine region, Slovenia. *Atmos. Environ.* 39, 7570–7579.

- Llanos, W., Kocman, D., Higuera, P., Horvat, M., 2011. Mercury emissions and dispersions models from soil contaminated by cinnabar mining and metallurgy. *J. Environ. Monit.*, 13, 3460-3468
- Ljubič-Mlakar, T., Horvat, M., Kotnik, J., Jeran, Z., Vuk, T., Mrak, T., Fajon, V., 2011. Biomonitoring with epiphytic lichens as a complementary method for the study of mercury contamination near a cement plant. *Environ. Mon. Assess.* ISSN 0167-6369, 181, 225-241.
- Logar, M., Horvat, M., Akagi, H., Ando, T., 2001. Determination of total mercury and monomethylmercury compound in water samples from Minamata Bay, Japan: an interlaboratory comparative study of different analytical techniques *Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, 15, 515-526.
- Lu, J, Y., Schroeder, W, H., Berg, T., Munthe, J., Schneeberger, D., Schaedlich, F., 1998. A device for sampling and determination of total particulate mercury in ambient air. *Analyt. Chem.* 70, 2403–2408.
- Lupšina, V., Horvat, M., Jeran, Z., Stegnar, P., 1992. Investigation of mercury speciation in lichens. *Analyst*, 117, 673 doi: [10.1039/an9921700673](https://doi.org/10.1039/an9921700673).
- Márcio, G., C., Leonardo, O, B., Priscila, N., Railson, O, F., Walessa, A., Bragança. A., Marcia, C, F, S., Wallace, G, Mileni, S, F., Aline Dionizio, M, B., Maria, E, C., Rafael R., 2019. Spinal cord neurodegeneration after inorganic mercury long-term exposure in adult rats: Ultrastructural, proteomic and biochemical damages associated with reduced neuronal density, *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 191, 110159, 0147-6513, <https://doi.org/10.1016/>
- Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning of Republic of Slovenia, 1995. Report on measurements and evaluation of air pollution in the surrounding of Salonit Anhovo. In Slovenian, 1995.
- Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning of Republic of Slovenia, 2004. Report on measurements of air pollution in Morsko. In Slovenian 2004.
- Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning of Republic of Slovenia, 2021. Agency of the Republic of Slovenia. <http://meteo.arso.gov.si/met/sl/>.
- Mlakar, T, L., Horvat, M., Vuk, T., Stergaršek, A., Kotnik, J., Tratnik, J., Fajon, V., 2010. Mercury species, mass flows and processes in a cement plant. *Fuel* 89, 1936–1945.

- Pavlish, J. H., Sondreal, E., Mann, M. D., Olson, E. S., Galbreath, K. C., Laudal, D. L., and Benson, S., 2003. Status review of Hg control options for coal-fired power plants. Fuel processing. Technol. 82(2-3), 82–165.
- Poissant, L., Hoenninger, G., 2004. Atmospheric mercury & ozone depletion events observed at the Hudson Bay in Northern Québec along with BrO (DOAS) measurements. RM Z- Materials and Geoenvironment, 51, 1722–1725.
- Sholupov, S., Pogarev, S., Ryzhov, V., Mashyanov, N., Stroganov, A., 2004. Zeeman atomic absorption spectrometer RA- 915C for direct determination of mercury in air and complex matrix samples, Fuel Process. Technol., 85, 473–485.
- Streets, D. G., Horowitz, H. M., Jacob, D. Z. Lu, L. Levin, A. F. H., E. Sunderland, E. M., 2017. Total Mercury Released to the Environment by Human Activities. Environ. Sci. Technol. 51, 5969-5977.
- Tekran, 2001. Model 2357A Principles of Operation, Tekran
- UNEP, 2018. Global Mercury Assessment 2018 report. UN-Environment Programme, Chemicals and Health Branch, Geneva, Switzerland.
- UNEP, 2019. Global Mercury Assessment. Sources, emissions, releases and environmental transport. UNEP Chemicals and Health Branch, Geneva, Switzerland. 978-92-807-3744-8.
- UNEP. Global Mercury Assessment, 2013. Sources, Emissions, Releases, and Environmental Transport; UNEP Chemicals Branch: Geneva, Switzerland.